

INFLUENCE OF CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION ON THE ADSORPTION OF DYESTUFFS BY THE INSOLUBLE PART OF THE HEAT-DEHYDRATED GUM ARABIC

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Gum arabic becomes partly insoluble in water when heated to 165°-170° and the insoluble part could adsorb only basic dyes irreversibly, exchanging Ca ions for basic dye ions; Freundlich's isotherm is followed in case of malachite green only. Congo red though being an acid dye is adsorbed from very low concentrations. Presence of sodium chloride in the dyeing bath prevents the adsorption of basic dyes.

Gum arabic is classified under acid polysaccharides; it is mainly a mixture of calcium and potassium salts of a very complex acid, called arabic acid ($C_{18}H_{142}O_{74}$), associated with galactan and araban. Amy (*Bull. soc. chim. Biol.*, 1928, 10, 1079) observed that gum arabic when heated to 100° acquired reducing properties which were originally absent. The same author has also noted (*Ann. chim.*, 1934, ii, 2, 287) that arabic acid when dehydrated is converted into insoluble acid, called metagummic acid, of about the same acid strength as arabic acid. This acid swells in water, is non-sticky and dissolves in dilute alkalies.

The present authors observed that gum arabic became partly insoluble when heated to 165°-170° in a dry state.

Freundlich and Poser (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1944, 6, 27) observed that the chemical constitution of a dyestuff affected its adsorption by alumina.

The object of our present work was to study the influence of the constitution of dyestuffs on their adsorption by the insoluble part of dehydrated gum arabic, constituting mainly calcium arabate.

In the present work the adsorption of dyestuffs of different classes by the insoluble gum arabic has been studied colorimetrically. Aqueous solutions of acid and basic dyes of different classes, varying in concentration from 0.06 to 0.3% were taken; p_H values and equivalent conductivities of all these solutions at various concentrations were determined to ascertain the relative degree of ionisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

a. The gum arabic (B. P.), pulverised, manufactured by the Alembic Co., Baroda, free from dirt and other impurities, with specific properties $\{[\eta]^{25} = -24.62$, moisture = 11.47%, ash value = 2.887%} was dehydrated completely by heating to 165°-170° in a porcelain dish, immersed in a linseed oil bath. The dehydrated gum was kept soaked in a large quantity of distilled water for 24 hours in a Winchester bottle and shaken from time to time; the washings were repeated till the filtrate gave no precipitate with absolute alcohol; insoluble gum settled down, whereas the soluble part was removed by syphoning off. The insoluble mucilage of the gum was then heated to

dryness over a water-bath, powdered and sieved through a piece of muslin. The same piece of muslin was used in the subsequent preparations of the insoluble gum to maintain uniformity of size of the particles.

The following dyestuffs (I. C. I.) were selected for the study of adsorption and their purity was tested by standard methods :—

Azo dyes : Bismark brown (basic), Congo red (acid), chlorozol, sky-blue (acid), chlorozol pink (acid).

Triphenylmethane dyes : Malachite green, oxalate (basic), crystal violet (basic), methyl violet (basic), Lissamine green (acid), aniline blue (acid).

Azine dyes : Safranine T. S. (basic).

Thiazine dyes : Methylene blue, zinc chloride double salt (basic), delphine blue (acid).

Oxazine dyes : Nile-blue, sulphate (basic).

Nitroso dyes : Naphthol green (acid).

To start with a stock solution of 0.3% dyestuff was prepared and the subsequent concentrations were obtained by the dilution of the stock solution. With all the dyes six concentrations viz., 0.3%, 0.24%, 0.18%, 0.15%, 0.12% and 0.06% solutions were used, and these strengths were converted into g. mole per litre for the purpose of comparing the adsorption of the various dyes worked out. The molecular weight and hydrogen equivalents of the dyes were taken from H. J. Conn ("Biological Stains", Third ed., 1942). After preparing the various dilutions, their p_H values and equivalent conductivities were found out.

To study the adsorption of the dyes, about 1 gram of the insoluble gum arabic was taken in a weighing bottle and heated in an air-oven to about 120° to drive off the moisture, stoppered and accurately weighed; the gum was transferred to 80 c.c. of the dye solution taken in a glass-stoppered pyrex glass bottle and the weighing bottle with lid was weighed again. The bottle containing exactly 80 c.c. of the dye solution and accurately weighed amount of the insoluble gum were kept in a water thermostat at 37°, and shaken from time to time. Exactly after 24 hours the dye solution was taken out from the thermostat, centrifuged to remove the suspended particles of the insoluble gum, and its strength was then found out by means of the Duboscq colorimeter. For each estimation a number of scale-settings, usually five, were taken, and before putting the dye solution the instrument was carefully adjusted for equality of illumination on the two sides.

TABLE I

Adsorption of various basic dyes.

The same initial conc. (0.003231 g. mols. per litre), calculated from the colorimetric values of B/D of the respective dyes, as in the adsorption tables (not given here).

Dyestuff.	M.W.	Adsorption (x/m).	Adsorption.
Bismark brown	461.186	0.002104 g. mol./lit.	65.12%
Malachite green (oxalate)	428.480	0.001002	31.01
Crystal violet	407.721	0.002230	69.02
Methyl violet	393.705	0.002094	64.80
Safranine T	364.654	0.002123	65.79
Methylene blue	793.380	0.001752	54.23
Nile blue	732.432	0.002036	63.02

TABLE II

The values of ' a ' and ' $1/n$ ' (Freundlich's constants) of different dyestuffs (Fig. 2).

Dyestuff.	Class.	M.W.	' a '.	' $1/n$ '.
Bismark brown	Azo	461.126	1.841	1.000
Malachite green	Triphenylmethane	928.480	2.661	0.4596
Crystal violet	"	407.721	2.089	1.014
Methyl.violet	"	393.705	1.778	1.000
Safranine T	Azine	364.654	1.778	1.000
Methylene blue	Thiazine	793.380	1.135	1.013
Nile blue	Oxazine	732.432	1.647	1.000

Influence of an Electrolyte on the Adsorption of Dyestuffs by Insoluble Gum Arabic

From the results of adsorption experiments it appears that basic colours from aqueous solution are tremendously adsorbed by the insoluble gum arabic. It became interesting to see if the presence of an electrolyte had any influence on their adsorption.

For this purpose 0.2N solution of sodium chloride was prepared, and 0.3%, 0.24% and 0.18% solutions of malachite green were prepared with this solution. To 80 c.c. of these dye solutions weighed amount of the insoluble gum was added and adsorption was measured as usual. The results of the experiment showed that there was no adsorption of the dye at all in presence of NaCl.

The reason for this was supposed to be the preferential adsorption of sodium ions (from the sodium chloride) to the cations of the dye. Hence, base-exchange between Na^+ ions and Ca^{++} ions (from the insoluble gum) seemed likely; and to be certain the following experiment was performed.

The dried insoluble gum (1.069 g.) was added to 80 c.c. of 0.2N-NaCl solution and left in a water thermostat at 37° for 24 hours; calcium was then estimated in the solution. The results of the experiment showed that 0.0137 g. of Ca^{++} was exchanged by Na^+ ions.

DISCUSSION

It is observed from the results in general that only the basic dyes are adsorbed by the insoluble gum arabic, and that acid dyes with the exception of Congo red in dilute solutions, are not adsorbed at all. Damlé, Forster and Kudva (*J. Indian Chem. Soc., Ind. & News Ed.*, 1943, 6, 30) obtained similar results when working with Green earth of Indian origin as a base-exchange body.

In presence of sodium chloride a basic dye does not get adsorbed at all; this has been found to be due to the preferential adsorption of the Na^+ to the cations of the dye.

Adsorption of all the basic dyes by the insoluble gum arabic was irreversible as the adsorbed dye could not be removed by washing with water repeatedly.

Fig. 1

It is observed from Table I that positive adsorption takes place in case of all the basic dyes. Hydration of the bone-dried gum is quite likely, but if hydration is considerable the decrease in free solvent would give an increase in the concentration; in other words the apparent adsorption would be negative. Since this is not the case and always a decrease in concentration of the dye solution occurs, hydration seems to be very low due to the large size of the adsorbed cation as shown by Jenny (*Kol.-Chem. Beih.*, 1927, 23. 428) in case of permittities.

There is only a slight difference in the adsorption of methyl violet, Bismark brown,

nile blue and safranine. This may be due to a slight difference in hydration as expected from the slight difference in the size of their basic radicals. The same table also shows that methylene blue (zinc chloride double salt) is comparatively less adsorbed and it is believed to be due to adsorption of zinc ions along with the basic ions of the dye.

Malachite green is least adsorbed and this may be due to partial dissociation of the dye at the dilutions used, as seen from the equivalent conductivity, making available only few cations for the base-exchange.

It is observed that Congo red though being an acid dye is adsorbed by the insoluble gum arabic. The dye is adsorbed only from the very dilute solution (68% adsorbed from 0.0017M solutions); and at higher concentrations there is no adsorption at all. No other acid dye is adsorbed in this way; they are not adsorbed even at lowest concentration; and the reason for such a behaviour of the dye is still not understood.

Fig. 1 shows that adsorption, x/m , when plotted against final concentration C' , gives straight lines in case of all the dyes excepting in case of malachite green which gives a parabolic curve; it being an oxalate is slightly dissociated and hence gets adsorbed like a weak electrolyte.

Fig. 2 shows that in the case of malachite green $\log x/m$, when plotted against $\log$

Fig. 2

CV—Crystal violet; B—Bismark brown; MV—Methyl violet; S—Safranin;
NB—Nile blue; MB—Methylene blue and MG—Malachite green.

C' , gives a straight line with slope $1/n = 0.4596$, meaning thereby that the usual Freundlich's adsorption isotherm $x/m = ac^{1/n}$ is obeyed.

The value of the adsorption exponent $1/n$, as seen from Table II, is nearly 1.0 for all chloride dyes (*i.e.* Freundlich's equation is not obeyed), but differs in case of malachite green which is an oxalate. The values of the intercept on ordinate 'a' (adsorption constant) from the same table do not show any general relation between adsorption and the chemical constitution or molecular weights of the dyes but, taking the dyes of the same class (triphenylmethane), namely malachite green, crystal violet and methyl violet, the value of 'a' increases with molecular weight.